

Assessing Courses of the Online Learning Agreement

How to use the Evaluation Tool

A guide for Higher Education Institutions

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AsCOLA is an acronym which stands for “Assessing Courses of the Online Learning Agreement”. An Erasmus+ Key Action 2 project, AsCOLA aims to enhance and digitalize the quality framework of Erasmus+ student mobility and contribute to closing the data gap in the quality aspect of higher education transformation. The project will help higher education institutions (HEIs) better monitor and assess their institutional performance in education activities related to their internationalization strategy and policy.

The project will achieve these objectives through multiple activities, namely:

- Creating an evaluation methodology of the courses offered to Erasmus+ students.
- Developing and piloting an online evaluation tool connected to the Online Learning Agreement.
- Carrying out training sessions and producing train-the-trainers material to equip HEIs with the necessary knowledge to use the tool effectively.

In this guide “How to use the evaluation tool”, we will discuss how you can use the tool as a HEI staff member. We will explain all steps and include screenshots for clarification.

Please note: Access to the Dashboard is managed at institution level. If you are interested in accessing the Dashboard, please refer to your International Relations Office (IRO) for further guidance.

Step 1: How to log-in

Log into the EWP Dashboard via <https://ewp-dashboard.eu/login> and fill out your email address and password.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `ewp-dashboard-dev02.it.auth.gr/login`. The page features the EWP Dashboard logo in the top left and a central login form. The form includes a 'Welcome back!' message, a prompt to enter credentials, and input fields for 'Email' and 'Password'. A 'LOGIN' button is positioned below the fields, and a link for 'Forgot your password?' is located to the right of the password field. At the bottom of the form, there is a link for users who do not have an account yet. Below the form, the text 'no more paper; no more time wasted.' is displayed, followed by links to general information, privacy policy, and support team.

EWP Dashboard

Welcome back!
Enter your credentials to access your account.

Email

Password [Forgot your password?](#)

LOGIN

Don't have an account yet? [Register your institution!](#)

no more paper; no more time wasted.

Discover general information about the EWP Dashboard and other frequently asked questions [here](#)
Find the updated Erasmus Dashboard Privacy Policy and Terms and Conditions [here](#)
For any other issue, don't hesitate to [contact our support team](#)

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How to view all course evaluations

- a) Go to the **Course Evaluations** tab via the menu on the left and select your preferred course.

The screenshot displays the EWP Dashboard interface. On the left, a vertical menu is highlighted with a red border, containing the following items: My University, OLA, Short Term, Applications, and Courses Evaluations. The main content area is titled 'Home Page' and features a welcome message: 'Welcome to EWP Dashboard!' followed by a paragraph of text. Below the text are two tiles: 'Knowledge Base' with a brain icon and 'Service Desk' with a question mark icon.

- b) To easily find a specific course, **apply filters** using the blue button in the top right corner.
- c) You can find courses via Course Code and/or Course Title.

Note: Course titles are inserted from OLA and appear as they have been stated by students. This may differ from the course catalogue!

EWP Dashboard

My University ^

- Ukraine Assistance

OLA ^

Short Term ^

Applications ^

Courses Evaluations

Courses Evaluations

Listing of Courses

Total Evaluations: 5 | Active Filters:

CODE	ECTS	INSTITUTION	TERM	TITLE
BA100-01	5	uni-foundation.eu	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	Business Administration
HTML01	6	uni-foundation.eu	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	HTML I
1234	5	uni-foundation.eu	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	Mathematics
MATH-102	0	uni-foundation.eu	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	Mathematics II
PL123	5	uni-foundation.eu	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	Programming Languages I

Prev 1 Next

View the evaluation data of the selected course

a) On the **evaluation page**, you can find information about the course/evaluation on top of the page.

EVALUATION INFO

ID	COURSE CODE	COURSE TITLE	ACADEMIC TERM	INSTITUTION
81573785-6b9d-4a0d-8655-d2d9ce8de7e6	BA100-01	Business Administration	First semester (Winter/Autumn)	uni-foundation.eu

Background info
General impression
Learning methods
Teacher
Cultural differences
Assessment
Evaluation
Concluding

What best describes your gender?

Female	Male	Non-binary	Other
46.67%	33.33%	13.33%	6.67%

Total: 15 evaluations

What is your age?

16-18	19-25
40%	60%

Total: 15 evaluations

EXPORT

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- b) Data from the evaluation is collected per **theme** of the survey (background info, general impression, etc.). Click the tabs above the data to select and review a theme from the evaluation survey.
TIP: Don't forget to scroll down on the pages to not miss any data; some results may take up more space than the screen allows for!
- c) You can export all data from the evaluation at once by clicking the **EXPORT-button** in the bottom-right corner.
TIP: Want to find out more about how to interpret the data and translate it into practice, read our guide on how to make effective use of the outcomes of the evaluation tool.

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